

Calibration of Spectroscopic Reflectometer for Thin Film Characterization

Md.Anzan-Uz-Zaman¹, Md.Aliuzzaman², Md. Abul Hossion³, Md. Nasrul Haque Mia¹, Md. Shah Alam¹, Himangshu Kumar Ghosh¹

¹ Institute of Electronics (IE), ² RECD, INST

Atomic Energy Research Establishment (AERE), Gonoakbari, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

³ Applied Physics, Electronics and Communication Engineering, University of Dhaka, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

E-mail: anzan.zaman@gmail.com, jonyphys@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT: Spectroscopic reflectometer is generally used for measuring the thickness of thin films. Optical techniques are used for this purpose. Optical techniques measure the thickness of thin transparent and semi-transparent layers by analyzing white light interference. Here we have done installation and calibration of a spectroscopic reflectometer at VLSI Lab, IE, AERE. Results regarding calibration are also discussed.

KEY WORDS: Thin film, Reflectometer, ARC, Thickness, Reflectance.

1. INTRODUCTION: A spectroscopic reflectometer is used for measuring the thickness of a thin transparent and semi-transparent layer. The instrument use optical techniques to determine thin film characteristics by measuring how the film interacts with white light. To perform the functions for which they were designed, thin films must have proper thickness, composition, roughness and other characteristics important to the particular application. These characteristics need to often be measured, both during and after thin film fabrication. Optical techniques are usually preferred for measuring thin films because they are accurate, non-destructive and require little or no sample preparation. The optical wave length range of this instrument is at a range of 380 nm to 1000 nm (White light) and repeatability $\pm 1\%$. The instrument can be used in the fields of (i) Solar Cell: ARC (anti-reflective coatings) Process (ii) TFT-LCD: SiO_x , SiN_x , Photo Resists, ITO Polyimide (iii) LED: SiO_x , SiN_x , ITO etc [1,2].

2. METHODOLOGY: The two most common optical measurement methods are spectral reflectance/ transmittance and ellipsometry. Spectral reflectance measures the amount of light reflected from a thin film over a range of wavelengths, with the incident light normal to the sample surface. Ellipsometry is similar, except that it measures reflectance at non-normal incidence and at two different polarizations. In general, spectral reflectance is much simpler and less expensive than ellipsometry, but it is restricted to measuring less complex structures.

Fig.1: Basic Diagram of Receiving the Reflected Light.

Fig.2: Principle of white Light Interference

The total system consists of five main units i.e. (i) light source (ii) PDA (Photo Diode Array) Box or Spectrometer (iii) Microscopic Unit (iv) Power supply unit for light source and (v) PC. Microscopic unit can be divided into four parts as (i) Manual Adjustable Magnification (ii) Fiber optic coupling with spectrometer (iii) Digital visualization camera and (iv) Auto focus based on SR system [3,4].

Fig.3 : A Simplified Block Diagram of the Spectroscopic Reflectometer.

The light bulb used here has a rating 6V, 20W. After turn on the lamp, it will take 10 minutes to be stable. Sample is placed to the stage under the microscope. A camera is attached to the microscope to see the view on PC screen. The stage is adjusted to focus on the sample and it is observed on PC. After stable the light source, light is incident on the sample and reflected light is carried out through the fiber optic cable to PDA Box. Fig.1 gives a basic idea how reflected light is collected by PDA Box/Spectrometer [4]. This unit translates the optical data into digital data which is fed to the PC. SR software manipulates the digital data to measure the thickness of the film. The amplitude and periodicity of the reflectance of thin films are determined by the films thickness, optical constants and other properties such as interface roughness. In reflectometry it is not possible to solve for film properties in closed form, nor it is possible to solve for n and k at each wavelength individually. In practice, mathematical models are used that describe n (Refractive index) and k (Extinct constant) over a range of wavelengths using only a few adjustable parameters. Film properties are determined by calculating reflectance spectra based on varying trial values of thickness and the n and k model parameters, until the calculated reflectance matches the measured reflectance best (Best-Fit-Algorithm).

3. THEORY: Reflectance is defined as

$$R = \frac{I_{refl}}{I_{inc}} \text{----- (1)}$$

where I_{inc} is the incident light intensity and I_{refl} is the reflected light intensity. The tool only measures reflected light intensity I_{refl} . To determine I_{inc} , it is necessary to measure a reference sample with a known reflectance R_0 –“referencing the reflectometer”. Reference I_{inc} can be easily derived from the expression [5,6].

$$R_0 = \frac{I_{r0}}{I_{inc}} \text{----- (2)}$$

Best measurements involve good knowledge of R_0 and good quality measurement of intensity. For calibrating the instrument, the stage is taken at the lowest point and then should wait for ten (10) minutes after on the light source to stable it. A small reference sample (TRF 008) is taken to the stage and the tilt part of the case of the sample is focused to check the background. If background curve is at the same range then the device is ready for next operation. The reference sample inside the plastic cover is now focused on and a measurement is done by clicking the spectrometer and reference icon of the SR software for referencing the reflectometer. Again the sample is focused on microscope and a physical measurement is done by clicking spectrometer and measurement icon. The reference sample contains a thin film layer of SiO_2 on SiCr substrate. To measure the thickness of SiO_2 film the following steps should be followed:

Fig 4: Flow chart for thickness measurement

4. RESULTS: The result of any measurement can be saved for further documentation. The result of calibration is given below:

Table 1: Material information

Index name	Material	Thickness μm	Type	n	K (550 nm)
Ambient	VOID			1.0	0.00
Layer-1	SiO_2	0.14709	EMA	1.466	
Substrate	SiCr			4.086	0.04

Table 2: Standard values

Material	Thickness μm	n	Wave length (λ) in μm
SiO_2	0.146 ± 0.0012	1.467	0.6238

>> Layer 1 << N & K Graphic

Graph 1: Reflectivity from sample for a range of incident light.

Table 3: Thickness of SiO₂ layer

No of observation	n	Thickness μm
1	1.46664	0.14702
2	1.46642	0.14701
3	1.46669	0.14699
4	1.46561	0.14708
5	1.46576	0.14708
6	1.46597	0.14706
7	1.46568	0.14704
8	1.46612	0.14703
9	1.46571	0.14709
10	1.46595	0.14709

5. DISCUSSION: The appropriate thickness of the reference sample is $146.4 \text{ nm} \pm 12\text{\AA}$ and $n = 1.467$ at $\lambda = 0.6238 \mu\text{m}$ as referred on the case of the sample. The calibration was taken ten times and from the table of the document it is observed that the average thickness of measurements is $0.14705 \mu\text{m}$, minimum $0.14699 \mu\text{m}$ and maximum $0.14709 \mu\text{m}$ which are within the range of the referred thickness. The n values also approximately equal to the referred value.

Table 4: Analysis of measurements

Result	n	Thickness μm
Minimum	1.46561	0.14699
Maximum	1.46669	0.14709
Range	0.00109	0.0001
Average	1.46606	0.14705
Unification	0.00037	0.00035
Standard	0.00038	0.00003

So, it can be said the calibration of the machine has been done perfectly. All the measurements were done under X10 lens. If more precision is needed then the table should be vibration free and lenses with more amplification factor can be used. But, still X10 lens is fit for our measurement.

6. FUTURE WORK: We have collected a sample coated with TiO₂ on glass substrate and Al₂O₃ on substrate from LED industry. We will measure the thickness of TiO₂ and Al₂O₃ layer in future.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: We are thankful to Charles Lin, Application Engineer, Radiation Technology Co. LTD. Taiwan, for his presence during installation and calibration of Reflectometer.

8. REFERENCES:

- [1] B. L. Sopori, Y. Zhang, W. Chen, and J. Madjdpour, "Silicon solar cell process monitoring by PV Reflectometer," *IEEE PVSC, Anchorage, AK, Sept, 2000*.
- [2] Bhushan Sopori, U. S. Patent No. 6,275,295.
- [3] B. L. Sopori, Reflectometer: Performance Testing / Error Analysis, 12th Workshop on Crystalline Silicon Solar Cell Materials and Processes, Aug, 2002.
- [4] B. Sopori, AR Coating Thickness on Si Solar Cells, NREL/CP-520-37478, Feb 2005.
- [5] B. L. Sopori, Principle of a new reflectometer for measuring dielectric film thickness on substrates of arbitrary characteristics, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **59(5)**, 725, 1988.
- [6] B. Sopori, Y. Zhang, Principles and Applications of Reflectometry in PV Manufacturing, NREL/CP-520-31003, Oct, 2001.